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Title: SOP for tryptophan metabolite analysis of stool/meconium via LC-QQQ

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Summary

Gut microbiota is an important factor affecting human health. The tryptophan metabolites (anthranilate, indole-3-acetate, indole-3-aldehyde, indole-3-lactic acid, *L*-kynurenine, *L*-tryptophan, *N*-acetyltryptophan) perform important signalling and immunomodulatory functions, especially interaction of the innate immune system of the host with PXR or AHR xenobiotic receptors. This protocol describe preparation of stool/meconium samples and quantitative/semiquantitative determination using LC-QQQ. Sample preparation of stool/meconium samples is complementary to the protein analysis and thus allows the simultaneous determination of tryptophan metabolites and proteins in stool/meconium samples.

Preparation

Safety information

- Stool/meconium are classified as a biohazardous material & thus all items in contact (e.g. pipette tips, vials) should be disposed of appropriately.
- Isopropanol: flammable liquids, eye irritation, specific target organ toxicity following single exposure

Equipment

- 100 μ L multichannel pipettes & 1 mL pipettes
- Centrifugal evaporator
- Mini vortex or vortex for 96-well plates
- Centrifuge with rotor for 96-well plates

Consumables & glassware

- 4 mL screw cap glass vial and cap
- 500 μ L 96-well plates with silicone sealing
- 100 μ L & 1 mL tips

Reagents for standard and sample preparation

- Stool/meconium swab stored in -80 °C freezer and thawed at room temperature
- 80% (v/v) isopropanol
- BCA kit for protein analysis
- Labelled standard mix:
 - [¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate acid (99% isotope enrichment) – harmful, irritating
 - [²H₅] L-kynurenine (99% isotope enrichment)
 - [¹³C₁₁][¹⁵N₂] L-tryptophan (99% isotope enrichment)
 - [¹³C₆] anthranilate (99% isotope enrichment) – harmful
- Indolmix (native standard mix) each = 250 nM in 25% (v/v) isopropanol
 - indole-3-acetic acid –harmful, irritating
 - L-kynurenine
 - L-tryptophan
 - anthranilate - harmful
 - N-acetyl-tryptophan – harmful, irritating
 - Indole-3-aldehyde - irritating
 - Indole-3-lactic acid - irritating

Reagents for mobile phase preparation

- Acetonitrile, LC-MS grade
- Formic acid (FA), LC-MS grade
- MilliQ water

Procedure

Standard preparation

1. Prepare 5 mL aliquots of 200 nM [$^{13}\text{C}_6$] indole-3-acetate acid, 50 nM L-kynurenine [$^2\text{H}_5$], 2000 nM L-tryptophan [$^{13}\text{C}_{11}$][$^{15}\text{N}_2$], 50 nM anthranilate [$^{13}\text{C}_6$] in 5% (v/v) isopropanol
2. Pipette directly or dry the internal reference standard mix down in Centrifugal evaporator at laboratory temperature, store in $-80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and reconstitute in the solvent before analysis.

Sample preparation

3. NOTE: Store stool/meconium swabs at $-80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
4. Take out stool/meconium swab from freezer and leave at room temperature for 30 min
5. Pipette 1 mL of 80% (v/v) isopropanol and vortex for 5 min at 1600 RPM at room temperature
6. Pipette 50 μL of extract to 96-well plates and dry the sample in Centrifugal evaporator
7. Redissolve in 50 μL of 5% (v/v) isopropanol standard mix containing: 200 nM [$^{13}\text{C}_6$] indole-3-acetate, 50 nM [$^2\text{H}_5$]L-kynurenine, 2000 nM L-tryptophan [$^{13}\text{C}_{11}$][$^{15}\text{N}_2$], 50 nM anthranilate [$^{13}\text{C}_6$] (use multichannel pipettes)
8. Sonicate 1 min
9. Vortex 2 min at 1600 RPM at room temperature
10. Centrifuge the samples 10 min at 4000 RPM (use centrifuge for 96-well plates)

Mobile phase preparation

- Mobile phase A: 0.1% (v/v) FA in milliQ water (solution can be kept for 7 days at $4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ temperature)
- Mobile phase B: 0.1% FA in 95% (v/v) acetonitrile

NOTE: use at least 5% milliQ water in acetonitrile (prevent LC clogging)

LC-QQQ analysis

11. Clean the source and nebulizer before measurement
12. Check solvent for needle rinsing
13. Check solvent for seals rinsing
14. Prepare mobile phase
15. Input sequence
16. Start LC-QQQ analysis run
17. Check initial blanks, standard mix = Indolmix, Labelled standard mix and QC

NOTE: If problems, stop run, cap samples and store at -20 °C whilst troubleshooting.

NOTE: Measure with every sample set:

- Instrument blank (Mobile phase A)
- Procedural blank (same preparation as samples; containing Labelled standard mix)
- QC (pool of samples extract; containing Labelled standard mix)
- QC dilution series in 3 replicates (same sample preparation as QC with 2x, 4x, 8x dilution & spiked with Labelled standard mix)
- Indolmix
- Labelled standard mix in 5% (v/v) isopropanol
- Calibration curve in matrix: prepare pool of stool/meconium sample extract → spike Labelled standard mix (use 6 different concentration) → measure 6 calibration points with 3 replicates (6 replicates for LOD, LOQ determination)
- QC_dilution series in 3 replicates (dilute QC: 2x, 4x, 8x & spike with same concentration of Labelled standard mix)

LC-QQQ sequence setup

- i. Clean_blank
- ii. Clean_blank
- iii. Instrument blank
- iv. Indolmix
- v. Indolmix
- vi. Indolmix
- vii. Labelled standard mix
- viii. QC_dilution series
- ix. Procedural blank
- x. QC sample
- xi. Samples 1-3
- xii. Instrument blank
- xiii. Sample 4-6
- xiv. Instrument blank
- xv. Sample 7-9 ...
 - a. NOTE: measure Instrument blank after every 3 samples
 - b. NOTE: measure Indolmix with every 30 samples
 - c. NOTE: measure Labelled standard mix minimum 3 times (at the beginning of the batch, in the middle of the batch and the end of the batch)
- xvi. Calibration
- xvii. End with Indolmix, Instrument blank and 2 x Clean blank

Table 1. SRM assay library for positive ion detection mode

COMPOUND	PRECURSOR	PRODUCT	RT [MIN]
L-KYNURENINE*	209.09	192.00	1.6
L-KYNURENINE	209.09	94.00	1.6
[² D ₄] L-KYNURENINE*	215.13	198.00	1.6
[² D ₄] L-KYNURENINE	215.13	96.10	1.6
L-TRYPTOPHAN	205.10	188.00	2.9
L-TRYPTOPHAN*	205.10	91.00	2.9
[¹³ C ₁₁] [¹⁵ N ₂] L-TRYPTOPHAN	218.10	200.00	2.9
[¹³ C ₁₁] [¹⁵ N ₂] L-TRYPTOPHAN*	218.10	98.10	2.9
ANTHRANILIC ACID	138.06	120.00	7.2
ANTHRANILIC ACID*	138.06	65.00	7.2
[¹³ C ₆] ANTHRANILIC ACID	144.08	126.10	7.2
[¹³ C ₆] ANTHRANILIC ACID*	144.08	70.20	7.2
N-ACETYLTRYPTOPHAN*	247.11	188.10	7.8
N-ACETYLTRYPTOPHAN	247.11	130.00	7.8
N-ACETYLTRYPTOPHAN	247.11	118.10	7.8
INDOL-3-LACTIC ACID	206.06	188.00	7.8
INDOL-3-LACTIC ACID	206.06	130.10	7.8
INDOL-3-LACTID ACID*	206.06	117.90	7.8
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE*	146.06	118.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	117.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	91.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	65.10	8.0
INDOLE-3-ALDEHYDE	146.06	39.20	8.0

* Transition used for quantification

SRM metabolite quantitative/semi-quantitative evaluation

18. For concentration determination of indole-3-acetic acid, *L*-kynurenine, *L*-tryptophan and anthranilate use internal standardization with isotopically labelled standards [¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate, [²D₄] *L*-kynurenine, [¹³C₁₁] [¹⁵N₂] *L*-tryptophan and [¹³C₆] anthranilate

The calculation is based on the concentration of isotopically labelled standard added to DBS sample, measured response (integrated peak area) of isotopically labelled standard, and response (integrated peak area) of metabolite Equation (1).

$$c_{met} = \left(\frac{CIS}{AIS} \times A_{met} \right) \quad (1)$$

19. For the lack of commercially available standards, the concentration indole-3-aldehyde, indole-3-lactic acid and *N*-acetyl tryptophan are determined with response factor (RF) Equation (2). NOTE: use [¹³C₆] indole-3-acetate as a C_{IS}.

$$c_{met} = \left(\frac{CIS}{AIS} \times A_{met} \right) : RF \quad (2)$$

RF are calculated from Indolmix and Labelled standard mix determined in Equation (3)

$$RF = \left(\frac{A_{met}}{AIS} \times \frac{CIS}{c_{met}} \right) \quad (3)$$

NOTE: final c_{met} normalize to total protein concentration (use BCA kit)

LC-QQQ method setup

Multisampler settings

Injection volume			2 μ L
Needle Wash			Multi-wash
Stoptime			As Pump/No Limit
Posttime			Off
Advanced	Sampling Speed	Draw Speed	100 μ L/min
		Eject Speed	100 μ L/min
		Wait time After Draw	0 s
	Needle Height position	Offset	-0.4 mm
		Use Vial/Well Bottom Sensing	Yes
	High Throughput	Sample Flush-Out factor	5.0
		Injection Valve to Bypass for Delay Volume Reduction	No
		Enable Overlapped Injection	No

Binary Pump

Flow	0.3 mL/min		
Solvents	A	0.1% (v/v) FA in milliQ water	
	B	0.1% (v/v) FA in 95% (v/v) acetonitrile	
Pressure limits	Min	0 bar	
	Max	1200 bar	
Stoptime	14 min		
Posttime	Off		
Advanced: Timetable	Time [min]	A [%]	B [%]
	0	95	5
	5	90	10
	10	5	95
	11.99	5	95
	12.00	95	5
	14.00	95	5

Column comp

Temperature	40 °C		
Advanced	Enable analysis	When temperature is within	\pm 0.8 °C

QQQ

Source parameters	Gas Temp:	160 °C	
	Gas Flow:	15 L/min	
	Nebulizer:	25 psi	
	Sheath Gas Temp:	250 °C	
	Sheath Gas Flow:	12 L/min	
	Capillary:	3500 V (Positive)	3000 V (Negative)

	Nozzle Voltage:	500 V (Positive)	1500 V (Negative)
iFunnel parameters	High Pressure RF	150 V (Positive)	90 V (Negative)
	Low Pressure RF	60 V (Positive)	60 V (Negative)
Chromatogram	Stop Time		
	No limit/As Pump		
	Ion source	AJS ESI	
	Time filtering	Peak width	0.05 min
Time segments	Start Time	Scan type	Div Valve
1	0	MRM	To MS
2	10.5	MRM	To Waste

Column & guard column: Acquity UHPLC CSHTM C18 column (100 x 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm) & VanGuard ACQUITY UPLC CSH C18 (5 x 2.1 mm; 1.7 μm) from Waters